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School Security Measures As Correlate Of Effective Administration In Public Secondary Schools In Rivers State

Okorafor, Pauline Onyekachi

**Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This study examined school security measures as correlate of effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The study was guided by 3 objectives, with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted correlational survey research design. The population of the study comprised 7,184 principals and teachers in 291 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 379 respondents were drawn from the entire population using Taro Yamane formula. The sampling technique was a proportionate stratified random sampling. The instruments titled: School Security Measures Scale (SSMS) and Effective Administration Scale (EAS). The instruments were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.87 for School Security Measures Scale and Effective Administration Scale respectively were derived using Cronbach alpha. The research questions were answered using simple regression, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level with the help of statistical package in social science (SPSS). Findings of the study revealed that presence of school security guards, installation of security gadgets, and adherence to security tips does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Hence, the study concluded that school security measures do not predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that government should staff schools with trained and qualified security guards to help to monitor and prevent delinquent behaviours, forestall breakdown of security rules, and foil attacks of intruders or criminal agents in order to enhance effective administration of schools. Also, government should partner with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to support in the installation security gadgets in schools to promote safe school environment for attainment of effective administration.

Keywords: School, Security Measures, Administration

INTRODUCTION

Education could be seen as an instrument for achieving socioeconomic and technological growth and development of any nation. It is an instrument par-excellence and the means of developing human intellect, technical skills, character and effective citizenship for self-reliance and effective national development (FRN, 2014). A simple way of appreciating education is that it is a tool or a necessary weapon that is needed by every human being in order to effectively navigate this complex world (Aguba, 2021). Education in essence is the most effective tool for academic progress, social mobilization, political survival and effective national development of a country, it constitutes the single largest enterprise in

Nigeria. The educational policy of any nation is to achieve education for all (E.F.A.). The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in the quality and efficiency of all level of education. Therefore, it is typical for an educational institution to sufficiently provide for its clients (parents, students, society, employers of labour, and other stakeholders), through the teachers and other staff, who are the direct channels through which educational objectives can be transmitted to learners. The school management is saddled with the task of overseeing the activities of students, and teachers for the actualization of effective administration.

Effective administration has to do with the degree to which it realizes its goals. It involves planning, organizing, co-coordinating, controlling and directing the activities of people within such establishment towards the achievement of the set out goals. In more specific terms, Peretomode as cited in Nayon (2017) said effective administration is concerned with applying rules, procedures, policies, that allows the accomplishment of defined common objectives within the organizational setting. He further said that it is an institutional position held by an incumbent giving the responsibility for offering leadership to a work group in order to achieve predetermined objectives. He stressed that administration is concerned with the performance of executive duties, the carrying of policies and decisions to fulfil a purpose and the control of the day-to-day running of an organization.

Furthermore, effective administration is the process whereby the school head as the chief executive of his staff controls them towards the achievement of the goals of the school system (Ezeocha as cited in Nayon, 2017). It involves knowledge of the structure of educational organizations and the administrative process that relates to the management of those organizations. Effective administration therefore is that administration that helps to bring about optimum achievement of any organization/establishment and in this case, the school. However, Nayon (2017) opined that the indicators of effective administration are regular teacher and students attendance, high students academic achievement, increase in graduation rate, high teachers satisfaction, discipline referrals, safe and secured environment, and many others. As noted by Nayon, security is one of the very most important indicators of effective school administration as it guarantees safe operation of the school.

Security has been defined as the degree of protection against danger, damage, loss and crime (Dwyer & Osher, 2020). Security is a form of protection where a separation is created between the assets and the threat. Security is the precaution taken to safeguard an environment from impending danger or injury. It is a measure taken to prevent dangers and threats. A place where there is security is a place of safety (Dwyer & Osher, 2020). The evidence of a secured school is the existence and execution of security measures which are well drawn policies of protection that should be given to the stakeholders within the school, be it learners, teachers and managers. Security in school can be explained as a situation where students and teachers as well as other school users are not exposed to any form of danger or risk of physical or moral aggression, accident theft or deterioration. Campbell as cited in Ike (2015) opined that security are the strategies and procedures required to coordinate the diverse activities of the school, protect and manage school violence, reduce security risks and ensure that the school environment is safe for teaching and learning. In other words, they are the school security measures taken to make the school environment safe.

School security measures are protective strategies and procedures that ensure a state of inviolability from hostile act or influences (Aryu, 2020). They are the plans for the protection that is given to the stakeholders within the school. The school is an organisation that needs to have planned security measures to protect its components so that the culture of learning and teaching is enhanced to guarantee effective administration. Stephen as cited in Ike (2015) saw security measures in school to include policies, guidelines and procedures required to co-ordinate the diverse activities of the institution in order to achieve safety. One of the central duties of the school manager is to ensure that security programmes are effectively implemented and that necessary steps are taken whenever situation arise which could be possibly unsafe. This is to say that school security measures are to be reinforced to keep the school stakeholders and the environment free from harm and danger.

Creating and maintaining secure environment needs clear understanding and measures by all stakeholders. They school know what the school has to do to enhance the security and the steps to take in the face of emergency. Stephen as cited in Ike (2015) asserted that it is essential that scholars and members of staff feel safe at school and it is for this reason that schools should have security measures in place which would be revised regularly. School with clear norms and expectations, fair procedures and the involvement of members of the community (educators, parents, learners, principals, administrators and community service) are less likely to experience high level of security threats (Aryu, 2020).

School remains one of the safest environments for children. However, in far too many schools in the country, security challenges threaten the teachers as well as the rights of students and which in turn affect quality education. Increasingly, students are victimised in school by fellow students, teachers as well as insurgency. Such security threats need to be defined, acknowledged and prevented. If drastic action is not taken, the existing security threats such as cult related activities, kidnapping, terrorism, bombing, armed insurgency robbery, lack of property physical security facilities like fences, bullying which can take a variety of forms, theft, arson and extortion, could spiral out of control, leaving large number of students fearful, injured and deceased. Thereby limiting the chances of increase in literacy level for the actualization of effective administration in the school (Gauster, 2018).

The above scenario demands a drastic action in order to address the safety and security of schools so as to prevent violence against students. Children who are students in various schools spread across the country are important to the country's human capital and can be developed to an optimum level by providing a safe and conducive school environment. Safe and Conducive environment of the school is dependent on security measures in the school. Some of these measures as identified by Arop and Owan (2018) and Aryu (2020) include; security training/orientation, installation of security gadgets and adherence to security tips.

Presence of school security guards is defined as the process whereby security personnel are deployed or are seen within and outside the school environment to help forestall any breach of security or law and orders that may impend the peaceful learning environment of the school. The presence of presence of security guards scares criminal away from the school, and thereby promoting atmosphere that guarantee the achievement of school goals (Aryu, 2020). More so, the installation of security gadgets in school can be defined as the setting up of security facilities within the school premises. It is the existence of security devices in the school that uses state-of-the-art technology to provide a higher level of protection within the school to ensure a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning activities.

In addition, adherence to security tip is defined as compliance or obedient to security guidelines and measures in the school. Security tips are important part of school security measures. Where there are no guidelines or tips to guide the ways the measures are conducted and implemented, the security facilities provided may become a problem instead of a protective device in schools. Security tips set guidelines and provides direction as to how avert security breach (Rogers & Schoeman, 2020). Priorities regarding school security have increased drastically and something needs to be done to ensure that violent acts such as kidnapping, vandalism, harassment, bulling, sexual molestation and harassment, possession and use of drugs, weapons, formation of gangs, shooting in schools and many others. It is against this background that this study is intended to examine the extent school security measures predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of Problem

In the period between 2012 and 2018, over 800 teachers were reportedly killed in attacks, while more than 19,000 were displaced. Statistics revealed that 1 in every 5 of the world's out-of-school children is in Nigeria. This could be attributed to insurgency, poverty, crime and violence perpetrated against schools. Media reports indicate that crime, violence, disorder, bombings, unknown gunmen invasion are the major problems facing public secondary schools in Nigeria. More so, fire outbreak, flood, drug addiction and abuse, gender-based violence, physical and humiliating punishment, bullying, exploitation, child trafficking; gang violence, cyberbully, abductions/kidnappings, hazardous materials in school environments and unsafe school facilities have left 2.8 million school students in need of education-in-

emergencies support, with over 1,392 classrooms damaged. Engagement in these activities sometimes have led to killings, destruction of properties and threats posed to individuals within the setup.

The consistent attacks and external invasion of criminals into secondary schools have put teachers and students into fear, and the damages caused is an indication that most of our secondary schools are not safe anymore. These problems not only endanger students and teachers but they also prevent effective administration in the school. This change in school climate has created an imperative need for schools to identify measures that can enhance the safety of all school users. This is because when people are legally required to attend school, school personnel have the corresponding duty to provide students and staff with a safe, secure and peaceful environment in which teaching and learning can occur. Although it has been witnessed that in few schools, some level of security preventive measures necessary to secure the school environment have been put in place such as the introduction of identity cards for students and staff, recruitment of security guards, and locking of schools doors/windows. But despite these efforts, the problem of school security threats persist and is on the increase and the researcher is bothered whether there is correlation between school security measures (such as presence of school security guards, installation of security gadgets, and adherence to security tips) and effective administration in public secondary. Hence, the problem of the study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was the extent school security measures predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. determine the extent presence of school security guards predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent installation of security gadgets predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. find out the extent adherence to security tips predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does presence of school security guards predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does installation of security gadgets predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does adherence to security tips predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Presence of school security guards does not predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Installation of security gadgets does not predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Adherence to security tips does not predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlation design. The population of this study consisted of all the 7,184 academic staff (i.e. 291 principals and 6,893 teachers) of 291 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size for this study was 379 respondents drawn from the entire population using Taro Yamane formula. The sampling technique was a proportionate stratified random sampling. This ensured that all members of the population are given equal opportunity of being selected. Questionnaire was the research instrument for the study and it was titled: School Security Measures Scale (SSMS) and Effective Administration Scale (EAS). The questionnaire are two, with two sections (A and B). Section A elicited

demographic information from the respondents, while section B elicited information on School Security Measures Scale and Effective Administration Scale. The two instruments were coded in line with the modified four-point Likert rating scale as follows; Very High Extent (HE) = 4 Points, High Extent (HE) = 3 Points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 Points, Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 Point respectively. Cronbach Alpha reliability statistics was used to test the reliability of the two instruments. The reliability coefficients of School Security Measures Scale and Effective Administration Scale are 0.81 and 0.87. For the data that were analyzed, simple regression was used to answer research question one to three, while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses one to three.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does presence of school security guards predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Extent Presence of School Security Guards Predicts Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.234 ^a	.055	.052	5.5%	Very Low extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 1 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .234 and .055 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .052. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 5.5% (.055×100). By implication, the result shows that presence of school security guards predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 5.5%.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does installation of security gadgets predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Extent Installation of Security Gadgets Predicts Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.007 ^a	.000	-.003	0.0%	Very Low extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 2 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .007 and .000 respectively, while the adjusted r square is -.003. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism) is 0.0% (.000×100). By implication, the result reveals that installation of security gadgets predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 0.0%.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does adherence to security tips predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression on the Extent Adherence to Security Tips Predicts Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	.119 ^a	.014	.012	1.4%	Very Low extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Table 3 revealed that the regression (r) and regression square (r²) coefficients are .119 and .014 respectively, while the adjusted r square is .012. The extent of prediction (i.e. coefficient of determinism)

is 1.4% (.014×100). By implication, the result reveals that adherence to security tips predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 1.4%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Presence of school security guards does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Presence of School Security Guards Significantly Predict Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	2.121	.136		15.606	.000	0.05	Accept H0 ₁
1 Presence of School Security	-.164	.035	-.234	-4.710	.072		

a. Dependent Variable: Effective Administration

Table 4 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are -.234 and -4.710. The p-value of 0.072 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, presence of school security guards does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: Installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Installation of Security Gadgets Significantly Predict Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.487	.099		15.043	.000	0.05	H0 ₃ Accepted
1 Security Gadgets	.004	.030	.007	.145	.885		

a. Dependent Variable: Effective Administration

Table 5 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are .007 and .145. The p-value of .885 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: Adherence to security tips does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Adherence to Security Tips Significantly Predict Effective Administration in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.509	.045		33.564	.000	0.05	H0 ₅ Accepted
1 Adherence to Security Tips	-.004	.015	-.014	-.281	.779		

a. Dependent Variable: Effective Administration

Table 6 revealed that standard beta value and t-test are -.014 and -.281. The p-value of .779 is higher than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, adherence to security tips does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed that presence of school security guards predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 5.5%. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that presence of school security guards does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings agree with Anderson (2018), Woodrow and Rich (2019), James and McCallion (2019) who found out in their studies that most public schools in developing countries like Nigeria does not have security guards, and this have affected that attainment of effective administration in these public schools. A possible explanation for these may be in fact that quite very recently, schools within North East and South East of Nigeria have experienced a lot of attacks like kidnapping and molestation which have result to shut down of schools within these areas have had to take care of managing physical hazards in schools. This is also tandem with Brooks, et al (2019) who opined that the likelihood of a student being violently victimized at school is extremely high in many West African countries. Students face a 1 in 2 million chance of dying at school due to lack of presence of trained security guards or personnel in the school. Evidences have shown that the absence of security guards in school increases crime and attacks on school, while presence of trained security guards in schools reduces the likelihood of a school shooting and other forms of crime and violence (Anderson, 2018).

The second finding of the study revealed that installation of security gadgets predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 0.0%. Similarly, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis shows that installation of security gadgets does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings corroborate the observation of Okere (2018) who found that in developed countries of the world, the installation and use of security gadgets as a means of keeping school environment safe has been found to be effective in forestalling attacks and all forms of school violence. The findings are also in line with Queensl and State School (2021) who in the study found that without the installation of security gadgets in schools, the school environment will be unsafe for school users, resulting to poor administrative system. But when schools are install with security gadgets, it builds a level of confidence among school personnel, because students and staff know that their surrounding have an eye that it can look around and guard them. Consequently, Williams (2019) advocated that there should be heavy installation of security gadgets in schools as it will positively predicts orderliness and deter criminal activities as well as violence. Ajayi (2017) further asserted that the installation of security gadgets in schools that are prone to attacks have significantly promoted safe environment for learning.

The third finding of the study revealed that adherence to security tips predicts effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 1.4%. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that adherence to security tips does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings agree with Trump (2020) who found out in his study that there is a low and insignificant relationship between compliance to security tips and safe learning environment for effective administration of schools. He attributed the reason to this negative relationship to non-compliance to security tips by school users. Also in line, Nnorom (2020) found that lack of adherence to security tips lead to disastrous consequences in school. School security threats are more common when there is no compliance to security tips by school users. Many crimes and hazards are bound to occur in schools when teachers, students and other school users fail to obey security tips. More so, DeWet (2018) and Netshitahaim and Van (2022) in their study found that for the schools to be a safe environment, schools authority should ensure that security tips are adhere by every member of the school including the visitors. Those preventive strategies or tips to security threat should be

implemented by all relevant authorities. Their study maintained that the total obedience to security tip are seen as the most effective way of managing security in schools for the attainment of effective administrative system. No wonder Uzuegbu-Wilson (2019) in their study revealed that there is a high and significant relationship between adherence to security rules and safe school environment. According to the scholar, when school users make effort to comply with safety tips, it promote a safe place for learning for effective administration of the school.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was deduced that presence of school security guards, installation of security gadgets, and adherence to security tips does not significantly predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Hence, school security measures do not predict effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government should staff schools with trained and qualified security guards to help to monitor and prevent delinquent behaviours, forestall breakdown of security rules, and foil attacks of intruders or criminal agents in order to enhance effective administration of schools.
2. Government should partner with Non-oernmNGOs to see how security gadgets or technologies can be installed in schools to promote safe school environment for attainment of effective administration.
3. School management should review their security tips and ensure effective compliance by all school users, this will help to keep the school in check and forestall any breakdown of security orders.

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